

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

Report on the procedure developed for the preparation of waste extracts

SPOKE N 6 Primary Agroindustry

Flagship project VINO

RM4- Don't waste the waste

DELIVERABLE D4.1

Version history

No.	Date	Details	Author(s)
0.1	2 nd October 2023	Initial draft	Elisabetta Tumminelli/Daniela Rossi
0.5	6 th November 2023	Draft implementation	Daniela Rossi
0.9	11 th December 2023	Draft conclusion	Daniela Rossi
1	22 nd December 2023	Final review	Daniela Rossi

This document is part of the project NODES which has received funding from the MUR – Missione 4, Componente 2, Investimento 1.5 – Creazione e rafforzamento di “Ecosistemi dell’innovazione”, costruzione di “leader territoriali di R&S” – del PNRR funded by the European Union - NextGenerationEU with grant agreement no. ECS00000036

Contents

GLOSSARY	3
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
A) MATERIALS AND METHODS	4
PLANT MATERIAL.....	4
CHEMICALS.....	4
INSTRUMENTS AND METHODS.....	4
<i>HPLC-UV analysis</i>	4
<i>Microwave-assisted extraction (MAE)</i>	5
B) EXTRACTION PROCEDURE SET-UP	5

Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to “Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
NODES’ Research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES’ Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES’ Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke’s ecosystem. It refers to “Spoke” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke’s ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke’ leadership and management. It refers to “soggetti affiliati” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”.
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In the perspective of vineyard waste recycling, activities carried out so far in RM4 focused on the set up of a green extraction procedure of pruning wood, which represents a huge waste material of viticulture, applying a Design of Experiment (DoE) approach. To this aim, Microwave-assisted extraction (MAE) was experimented, showing both economic and practical advantages: short extraction times, low use of solvents and good protection against thermolabile compounds. Additionally, it has high extraction efficiency, high reproducibility and robustness.

A) Materials and Methods

In this section chemicals (e.g. standards and solvents), instruments and methodologies used (e.g. for HPLC-UV analysis and MAE) are reported.

Plant material

One-year old lignified shoots of *Vitis Vinifera* Syrah were collected from 16 years old vines in the collection vineyards of the University of Turin (DISAFA vineyard; 45 30530 0 N, 7350320 0 E) in Grugliasco (TO), Italy on 02 February 2023. The DISAFA vineyard, planted in 2008, has a density of 4400 vines/ha and is situated 293 m above sea level in a flat area. Vines are vertically shoot positioned and trained to the Guyot pruning system. The soil composition is sandy; further details can be found in Catoni et al. (2012). Integrated agricultural management practices are applied. Syrah is grafted on SO4 (*Vitis berlandieri* x *Vitis riparia*). After collection, plant material was cleaned, cut and left to dry in a ventilated stove at 35°C until constant weight and then stored in a dark, dry place. Before extraction, plant material was finely chopped using a blade-mill (A10 IKA-Werke GmbH & Co., Staufen, Germany).

Chemicals

HPLC-grade solvents were supplied by Honeywell (Seelze, Germany), while analytical grade solvents were supplied by PanReac (Barcelona, Spain). Formic acid was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Milan, Italy).

Trans-Resveratrol and ϵ -Viniferin were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Milan, Italy).

Instruments and methods

HPLC-UV analysis

All analyses were carried out using a JASCO (Jasco Europe, Cremella, Italy) bench-top HPLC system, including a quaternary pump model PU-4180, autosampler model AS-4050 with a 5 μ L loop installed on purpose, column thermostatic compartment model CO-4065, and an UV-Vis photodiode array detector model MD-4010. The system was fully operated by the JASCO

ChromNAV software (version 2.04.03) operating in Microsoft Windows 7 Professional environment.

HPLC analyses were performed at 25°C using a Hibar® HR Purospher® STAR RP-18 endcapped column (2.1 mm ID x 100 mm, particle size 3 μ m), eluting with water containing 0.1% (v/v) formic acid (A) and acetonitrile containing 0.1% (v/v) formic acid (B). The eluent was applied onto the column in gradient mode starting from 5% to 40% of B in 4 min, a second gradient from 40% to 50% of B in 9 min, a third gradient up to 80% of B in 7 min which was followed by an isocratic elution phase for 5 min. The column was reconditioned by eluting from 80% of B to 5% of B in 0.1 min and with a final 15 min isocratic elution at the initial conditions (5% of B). The flow rate was 0.2 mL min⁻¹.

Target stilbenes (*trans*-Resveratrol and ϵ -Viniferin) were identified by comparing retention times and UV spectra of authentic reference standards to those of the compounds detected in wood extracts. In figure 1 the chromatogram of the target stilbenes is reported as an example (λ = 306 nm).

Figure 1

Microwave-assisted extraction (MAE)

All extraction experiments were conducted under microwave irradiation in a microwave mono-mode oven (Discover® Lab-Mate instrument, CEM Corporate, Buckingham, UK) equipped with a power and temperature controller. Extracts were evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure using a Heidolph Laborota 4000 instrument (Heidolph Instruments GmbH & Co., Schwabach, Germany) and/or using a Smart Evaporator C1 (Stepbio, Bologna, Italy).

B) Extraction procedure set-up

In this section the set-up of a green extraction procedure of *Vitis vinifera* pruning wood, applying a Design of Experiment (DoE) approach, is reported.

To set up of a green extraction procedure of pruning wood from *Vitis Vinifera*, Microwave-assisted extraction (MAE) was experimented as a valuable extraction methodology alternative to maceration and Ultrasound-Assisted Extraction (USAE). To this aim, a Design of Experiment (DoE) approach was applied. In contrast with the classic “one factor at a time” approach, DoE permits the study of the influence of multiple factors simultaneously.

As the first step, preliminary investigations were carried out to identify the experimental parameters to be included into the DoE experimental plan as well as those parameters that will be kept constant. Secondly, an experimental extraction plan was designed to study three responses, namely the peak area of the two main analytes present in the extract, *trans* resveratrol and ϵ -viniferin, Y1 and Y2, respectively, and the total extraction yield, Y3 (calculated as milligrams of dry extract per milligrams of dried plant material \times 100). Basing on the results obtained from preliminary investigations, three experimental parameters were evaluated: solvent composition -X1 (%ethanol-%water ratio from 20/80 to 80/20), duration of the MAE cycle -X2 (from 5 to 15 minutes), and temperature - X3 (from 40 to 80°C). All other parameters (e.g., amount of dried material, volume of solvent, type of vessel), including the operator, were kept constant.

For each experiment, once the microwave extraction cycle was completed, the mixture was filtered, the filtrate evaporated to dryness and then dissolved with a H₂O/MeOH 20/80 (v/v) mixture to have a final concentration of 10 mg mL⁻¹. All samples were filtered through a 0.45 μ m filter and placed in a vial for HPLC-UV analysis for the evaluation of responses Y1 and Y2.

Results clearly evidenced that the peak area of both *trans* Resveratrol (Y1) and ϵ -Viniferin (Y2) is extremely influenced by the extraction solvent (X1): higher is the ethanol percentage higher are the responses Y1 and Y2, thus suggesting that extraction of *trans* Resveratrol and ϵ -Viniferin occurs more effectively when ethanol is used as solvent. As far as the other two parameters are concerned, both the duration of the extraction cycle (X2) and the extraction temperature (X3) exert only a slight influence on both Y1 and Y2. Finally, concerning Y3, the coefficient derived from the statistical analysis highlighted that none of the considered factors significantly affected the responses.

Basing on DoE results, the best MAE conditions for the extraction of *trans* resveratrol and ϵ -viniferin from *Vitis Vinifera* pruning wood were identified (Table 1). The extraction method involves 100% EtOH as extraction solvent, a 5-minute microwave cycle at a temperature of 80°C with a microwave power of 50W, using a 20% (w/v) plant material-solvent ratio (e.g. 400mg of plant material extracted using 2 mL of solvent).

Solvent	MAE conditions				Plant material/solvent ratio (w/v)
	Power	Temperature	Number of cycles	Cycle time	
Etanol	50 W	80°C	1	5 min	20% (g mL ⁻¹)

Table 1

The optimized MAE extraction procedure will be applied to pruning wood of different *Vitis vinifera* cultivars (Pinot, Nebbiolo, Cabernet, Syrah) collected from 16 years old vines grown at the experimental vineyard of DISAFA – Unito, Grugliasco as well as to pruning wood of *Vitis vinifera* from Oltrepo' Pavese and Langhe.